

POLYMER-METAL COMPOSITE FILMS

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Summary

Simultaneous deposition of polymer and metal evaporated from separate sources results in a three dimensional dispersion of metal islands within a polymer matrix. Of the polymers and metals investigated, the mixture of polyethylene with copper is of most interest, exhibiting after annealing sheet resistivity changes from 10^{13} to 10^7 ohm per square when heated through 200°K . The electrical conduction mechanisms have been examined for both d.c. and a.c. conditions.

Introduction

The vacuum evaporation of a number of solid polymers has been shown to lead to deposits which exhibit properties remarkably similar to those of the respective bulk materials (1,2). Mass spectrometric analysis has indicated that considerable thermal degradation occurs during evaporation, but that molecules arriving at a substrate do recombine to form a sort of polymeric material (3,4). Optical absorption spectra of such materials show only minor differences from spectra of the original bulk polymer (4).

In the early stages of growth of vacuum deposited metal films, a characteristic island structure is produced, the film exhibiting a negative temperature coefficient of resistance. By the simultaneous deposition of metal and polymer we have

succeeded in reducing coalescence of the metal islands as the film thickness increases, and have produced instead of a uniform metal film, a three dimensional dispersion of metal islands within a polymer matrix. The structural and electrical properties of this class of material are strongly dependent on the relative proportions of each phase - particularly that of the metal, and on post-deposition annealing treatments. In the case of evaporated polymer films intended for use as insulators or encapsulants it is often advantageous to irradiate the substrate during and immediately after deposition with ultra violet light to induce cross-linking(5). Irradiation is not applicable in the case of composite films in which some small degree of metal island growth may be desirable, and which would be prevented if the polymer were too tough.

Composite films have been prepared using a number of polymers and metals (6). Polymers used include polyethylene, polycarbonate, melinex and polyvinylidene fluoride. Metals have included chromium, aluminium, gold, silver and copper. Tellurium has also been used as an example of an elemental semiconductor. The effect of different polymers on the structure and electrical properties of the films is too small to be detectable and because of our previous experience with evaporated polyethylene films it was decided to adopt this as our normal polymer.

Of all the combinations of polymer and metal we have examined the most interesting composite was found to be the mixture of polyethylene and copper. Results for this material are reported in detail. In all cases the final film thickness was approximately 900 Å.

Experimental Procedure

Deposition parameters

The experimental arrangement within the vacuum evaporation system is shown in Figure 1. Solid polymer pellets were evaporated from a source similar to that described previously at temperatures of the order of 650°K (1). The deposition rate was calibrated using a quartz crystal thickness monitor and subsequently maintained at any desired rate by manual control of the source heater current. This crude method of control was possible due to the large thermal mass of the source.

Metals were evaporated from a molybdenum strip source, the power to which was supplied by an automatic evaporation control system. The two sources were mounted as close together as practicable and shielded in such a manner that co-deposition was only possible in the area occupied by the substrate.

Corning 7059 glass substrates were positioned horizontally about 20 cm above the sources; substrate temperature was maintained throughout all depositions at 300°K. Chamber pressure rose to about 10^{-4} torr during deposition, mainly due to the light fragments produced during the thermal degradation of the polymer. Electrical connection to the film was by means of gold lands deposited from a third evaporation source. For surface conductivity experiments five samples of differing areas were deposited on the same substrate; for high field measurements samples were deposited in the form of planar capacitors. The deposition rate of polyethylene was maintained constant throughout at 17 \AA min^{-1} . Copper was deposited at various rates within the range 25 - 70 \AA min^{-1} .

Annealing phenomena

The electrical properties of all films tended to exhibit instabilities prior to annealing. Films were therefore annealed in situ at temperatures up to 493°K; higher temperatures caused unacceptable film softening. The change in surface resistivity was observed during annealing at a number of fixed temperatures by raising the temperature by increments of 12°, maintaining it at each new value for 15 minutes, and then determining the value of resistivity. Random checks confirmed that annealing was completed at each temperature within the 15 minute period. Annealing was also carried out at several different temperatures for periods of up to two hours, after which no further change in resistivity was observed.

The change in surface resistivity during annealing for a number of annealing temperatures is shown in Figure 2. Annealing at temperatures above 350°K brings about a dramatic change in the temperature coefficient of resistance. For two films annealed respectively at 375°K and 493°K, Figure 3 shows the relationship between surface resistivity and $1/T^4$; the curve for the film annealed at the higher temperature exhibits a change in resistivity of almost seven orders of magnitude for a change in temperature of 200°K. The straight line relationship obtained indicates that conduction is by a type of hopping process, which is considered in more detail in a later section.

Structural Examination

In Figures 4 and 5 are shown respectively transmission electron micrographs of polyethylene copper films taken immediately after deposition, and after annealing at 423°K for two hours. In each case the island size is approximately the same ($\sim 100 \text{ \AA}$ in diameter), but the inset electron diffraction patterns confirm that the copper of Figure 4 has been mainly converted to cuprous oxide in Figure 5. Oxidation occurred equally effectively if annealing was carried out under partial vacuum followed by

admission of air or oxygen, or entirely at atmospheric pressure.

Films annealed for two hours at the slightly higher temperature of 493°K could not be removed from the substrate for electron microscopy. Films annealed for five hours at 423°K were found to contain only copper oxide.

Electrical Properties

Two sets of films have been examined in detail, annealed at 493°K and 423°K respectively. In the first case the film consists essentially of Cu_2O islands immersed in polymer. In the case of films annealed at 423°K, however, the conversion of copper to Cu_2O is only partially complete, and we believe that the centres of the oxide islands still consist of copper. We have observed therefore two different conduction processes but for the purpose of this paper we describe only results applicable to the fully converted films. Electrical measurements were made parallel to the film surface for low field observations, and perpendicular to the film surface for high field observations. Measurements were carried out with the films in a vacuum cryostat over the temperature range 100°K to 350°K. Breakdown field strength was of the order of $6 \times 10^7 \text{ Vm}^{-1}$, a value similar to that obtained for polyethylene films (4).

D.C. measurements

Current-voltage-temperature characteristics are shown in Figure 6 for films annealed at 493°K. The general form of the characteristics are similar to those reported by other workers for a number of completely different materials, e.g., silicon oxide and zirconium oxide (7,8).

We have followed the principles of analysis described by Hill, and have obtained a normalised curve for the set of characteristics, which is shown in Figure 7 (9,10). It is seen that the datum locus (the near vertical line) is a good straight line and the fit of normalised data to a sinh curve is very good.

We can represent our I/V/T characteristics by an expression of the form

$$J = A T^n \exp(-B/T^{\frac{1}{4}}) \sinh(CF/T^{\frac{5}{4}})$$

in which B is a hopping constant similar to that used by Mott and is equal to $2.31 (2\alpha^3/\pi N_t k)^{\frac{1}{4}}$, where N_t is the trap density, a uniform trap distribution being assumed. A and C are constants, and F is field.

Separating this equation into two parts representing respectively temperature and field dependence, we have

$$J = J A^{-1} T^{-n} \exp (B / T^{\frac{1}{4}}) = \sinh (C F / T^{\frac{5}{4}})$$

For our films the best fit is obtained with $n = 1$.

From the normalised data we have constructed the plot of effective current, J , versus $1/T^{\frac{1}{4}}$ shown in Figure 8. This confirms that the films annealed at 493°K have one conduction mechanism over the entire experimental temperature range. We estimate that for the best films the density of traps $N_t = 10^{18} \text{ eV}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and that the decay constant $1/\alpha = 11 \text{ \AA}$.

A.C. measurements

The variation of a.c. conductance with frequency and temperature is shown in Figure 9 for a film annealed at 493°K. At temperatures of below 223°K the presence of dielectric relaxation loss peaks can be observed; they move towards lower frequency as the temperature is reduced. Figure 10 shows for the same film the variation of the real and imaginary parts of the permittivity, and again the relaxation peaks in ϵ'' are obvious. At any given temperature the value of ϵ' falls to half its low frequency value at the frequency at which the corresponding peak in ϵ'' occurs. By plotting this value of frequency (ω_{max}) against $1/T$ we obtain the results shown in Figure 11.

Discussion

The production of copper oxide films is usually brought about by the high temperature oxidation of copper. By producing a dispersion of copper particles within a polymer matrix we have been able to obtain films with the properties of copper oxide at much lower temperatures. The role of the polymer appears to be to prevent coalescence of the copper islands during deposition, and to allow each island to oxidise separately. At the annealing temperatures used most of the polymer is lost, the overall film thickness reduces, and the separation between islands reduces to about 10 \AA (11). Any effect that this thickness of polymer may have on the conduction mechanism largely controlled by the copper oxide is likely to be small. We consider that the mechanism is essentially that of hopping between traps in localised states close to the Fermi level.

The most significant feature of the films is the large variation in specific resistivity with temperature, and this we have begun to investigate for the purposes of producing temperature-sensitive devices.

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1. Experimental arrangement of vacuum deposition apparatus.

2. Sheet resistance vs reciprocal temperature for polyethylene-copper films for five annealing temperatures.

3. Sheet resistance vs $1/T^{1/4}$, replotted from Figure 2 for the two highest annealing temperatures.

4. Structure of polyethylene-copper film immediately after deposition.

5. Structure after annealing for two hours at 423° K. The inset electron diffraction pattern indexes as a mixture of copper and Cu_2O .

6. I-V-T characteristics for films annealed at 493° K.

8. Effective current vs $1/T$, replotted from Figure 7.

9. A.C. conductance vs frequency and temperature.

10. Real and imaginary values of permittivity vs frequency.

11. Relaxation peak frequency vs $1/T$